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1 Introduction

In statistical cloud schemes the cloud fraction is directly related to the normalized saturation deficit (Q1). This Q1 is determined by the distance of the (gridbox) mean state to the mean saturation normalized by the horizontal variance of the atmospheric state. Estimates of the horizontal variance of the conserved atmospheric state variables (e.g. liquid water potential temperature θ_l and total water q_t) are therefore needed. Up to now, statistical cloud schemes have been used frequently in combination with diffusion schemes for turbulent transports. At present mass flux schemes have proven to be more successful than diffusion schemes to represent turbulent fluxes in shallow cumulus layers. Therefore it is natural to combine the mass flux approach with a statistical cloud scheme. In order to do this estimates of the horizontal variance due to mass flux activity are needed. We obtained estimates of the variances of q_t from a simplified budget equation for the horizontal variance (section ??), and combined this with a simple statistical cloud scheme. To illustrate the strength of this approach, results of a Single Column Model (SCM) (described in section ??) for the intercomparison cases in GCSS Working Group 1 of Cumulus clouds (BOMEX and ARM) are shown and compared with Large Eddy Simulation (LES) results from the KNMI/IMAU model (section ?? and ??).

2 Variance

Our method of estimating the horizontal variance is similar to the Cumulus cloud scaling by Grant and Brown (1999). From the mass flux scheme we have M : the mass flux and q_t^u : total water water updrafts. We define the following convective velocity scale:

$$(w_*^{cu})^3 = \int_{cloud} \frac{g}{\theta} M \Delta \Theta_v dz,$$

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where $\Delta \Theta_v$ is difference between the potential temperature of the updrafts and the mean potential temperature: $\Delta \Theta_v = \Theta_v^u - \Theta_v$.

In order to obtain an estimate of the variance of q_t we use a simplified second order budget for the variance $\overline{q_t^2}$:

$$\overline{w' q_t'} \frac{\partial q_t}{\partial z} = \tau^{-1} \overline{q_t^2}.$$

This equation represent the balance between production of variance (left-hand side) and dissipation closed by a linear damping (right-hand side). In this equation τ is timescale associated with the updrafts in the Cu clouds:

$$\tau = l_{cloud} / w_*^{cu},$$

with l_{cloud} the cloud depth. Using a mass flux approximation for the production term, we get the following balance:

$$M (q_t^u - q_t) \frac{\partial q_t}{\partial z} \simeq \frac{w_*^{cu}}{l_{cloud}} \overline{q_t^2}.$$

This equation states the balance between production on the large Cumulus convective scale and dissipation on the smaller scale. We now arrive at the following expression for the variance

$$\overline{q_t^2} \simeq \frac{M (q_t^u - q_t) l_{cloud}}{w_*^{cu}} \frac{\partial q_t}{\partial z}.$$

3 Model

We used a SCM containing the following physical schemes:

- **Turbulence Scheme**

A simple E - l closure with a diagnostic length scale l and a prognostic equation for turbulent kinetic energy is used. The length scale consists of a quadratic length scale profile in the (unstable) boundary layer. At the top, in the stably stratified inversion a buoyancy length scale ($c \frac{\sqrt{E}}{N}$ with N^2 the Brunt-Vaisaila frequency) is used. The turbulence scheme satisfies the following conditions for a surface driven dry convective boundary layer: 1) $E_{max} = 0.4 w_*^2$, 2) $K_{max} = 0.1 h w_*$, and 3)

$\overline{w'\theta'}|_{entr} = -0.25\overline{w'\theta'}|_{surf}$ (with E_{max} the maximum of E in the BL, $w_*^3 = g/\theta h\overline{w'\theta'}|_{surf}$ the convective velocity scale, and h the height of the BL).

- **Mass Flux Scheme**

The mass flux scheme described in Siebesma and Cuijpers (1995) is used. In this scheme we made a few important modifications: 1) instead of the moisture convergence closure, we used for the cloud base mass flux $M_{base} = 0.03 w_*$, and 2) we took out the numerical diffusion of the mass flux scheme, and replaced it with a more “physical” prescription of diffusion. This diffusion is given by

$$K_{mf} = c l_{cloud} M$$

with $c = 0.1$.

- **Cloud Scheme**

As described above, the cloud fraction is diagnosed from a normalized saturation deficit (for simplicity, here only based on q_t):

$$Q_1 = \frac{q_t - q_{sat}}{\sqrt{q'^2}}$$

The cloud fraction is (Cuijpers and Bechtold, 1995)

$$B = 0.5 + 0.36 \arctan(1.55Q_1)$$

The SCM runs have been performed on a high, 40 meter vertical grid spacing.

4 BOMEX

We ran a 8 hour simulation of the GCSS WG-1 BOMEX case. This case is a simulation of shallow Cumulus clouds. The case is in near equilibrium, and the LES results of the LES model intercomparison (Siebesma et al., 2000) show that all LES models remain very close to their initial profiles. The results of the SCM are compared with a high resolution run of the KNMI LES model.

In Fig. ?? results for θ and q_t after 8-hours of simulation are plotted in order to investigate whether or not the SCM is able to simulate and retain a realistic mean state. Results show a very good agreement between LES and SCM results [Note, that this may not be too surprising, because the mass flux scheme

is tuned to the BOMEX case in Siebesma and Cuijpers (1995). On the other hand, experiments show that the modifications in the massflux scheme, and the robust behavior of the turbulence scheme have a large positive impact too].

Figure 1: Potential temperature and total water after 8 hours simulation of BOMEX.

We then compared our estimate of the horizontal variance of q_t with the LES output. Results (shown in Fig. ??) show a good structure and amplitude. On the downside, the variance in the middle of the cloud is clearly overestimated, and the peak near cloud top is located to low in the inversion.

The simulated cloud fraction (Fig. ??, bottom) reflects this behavior. Cloud fraction in the middle of the cloud is too high and the cloud top is located too low.

5 ARM

The GCSS WG-1 ARM case is a simulation of the daily cycle of Cumulus clouds above land. This case is based on an idealization of observations made at the Southern Great Plains ARM site on 21st June

Figure 2: Horizontal variance of q_t and cloud cover after 8 hours simulation of BOMEX.

1997. However, although it is a case above land, it is not a real interactive case as the surface fluxes of heat and moisture are prescribed.

To illustrate the general behavior of the SCM model, we plotted in Fig. ?? the time evolution of θ and the cloud cover. The plot of θ shows a gradual growing dry convective boundary layer during the first morning hours. At 17.00 UTC clouds start to developed, and the boundary layer evolves to a Cumulus topped boundary layer. Note that all fields are very smooth, reflecting that the combined schemes (section ??) are well behaving in a numerical sense.

These results are generally in good agreement with the LES results of this case, although there are some differences. In particular these are related to q_t and the cloud cover. In the LES model first clouds appear at 16 UTC; maximum cloud cover (of around 15 at 18 UTC, where-after a nearly linear decrease occurs. Clouds die out at 24 UTC. As shown in Fig. ?? all these features occur 1 (appearance and disappearance clouds) to 4 hours (maximum cloud cover) later in the SCM.

Figure 3: Time evolution of θ and cloud cover for the ARM case. Note that 11.30 UTC corresponds to 5.30 local time.

To illustrate the (dis)agreement more precisely we compared profiles of θ and q_t at 22.30 UTC. At this time the cloud layer is well developed. The potential temperature θ in Fig. ?? shows a 1000 m thick conditionally unstable layer; LES and SCM agree very well. For q_t differences are larger. In general, q_t is too large near cloud base, and the profile is too smooth. LES profiles show a clear bent in the slope of q_t near cloud base.

The estimate of $\overline{q'^2}$ (shown in Fig. ??) is clearly affected by the errors in the mean profile of q_t . Although the order is about correct, the structure is clearly not. The model misses the peak near cloud base, where to profile is too smooth. Simulated cloud fraction is too high, caused by the too moist profile and too high estimate of the variance.

Figure 4: Potential temperature and total water at 22.30 UTC of the ARM case.

6 Summary

We combined a simple statistical cloud scheme with a mass flux approach to estimate horizontal variance of q_t , and tested the behavior of this scheme in a SCM for two GCSWG-1 Cumulus cloud cases. Results of the SCM show the clear potential of this approach: results for the BOMEX case show a very good agreement with LES results; results for the ARM case show a reasonable agreement in the amount of clouds and the order of the variance, although some features in time and space are now clearly missed.

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Figure 5: Horizontal variance of q_t and cloud cover at 22.30 UTC of the ARM case.

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